

Isolation and quantitative analysis of thiophenes from *Tagetes* species by HPLC[†]

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Manuscript received 1 March 2001, accepted 12 November 2001

Quantitative evaluation of thiophenes content in three *Tagetes* species, viz. *T. minuta*, *T. patula* and *T. erecta* has been carried by HPLC. Six compounds, namely, 2,2' : 5'2''-terthienyl, 5-(3-buten-1-ynyl-2,2'-bithienyl), β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, octacosanol and 3-octacosanylstigmasterol have also been isolated from *Tagetes minuta* roots.

A genus of herbs, commonly known as Marigolds, a native of Mexico and other warmer parts of America, has naturalized elsewhere in the tropics and subtropics¹. Many *Tagetes* spp. yield aromatic essential oils known as 'Tagetes oil'. The oil is obtained from the entire aerial parts of the plant by steam distillation. Tagetes oil is commercially produced from *T. minuta* and *T. patula* in France, Kenya and India¹. *Tagetes minuta* oil exhibits bronchodilatory, tranquillizing, hypotensive, spasmolytic and anti-inflammatory activities², and shows juvenile hormone activity against *Dysdercus koenigii*³. The plant shows photosensitization and antiviral activities due to the presence of thiophenes⁴.

Thiophenes are common to *Asteraceae* family and possess one or more aromatic five-membered sulfur rings and are natural biocides⁵. Volatile oil extracted from *Tagetes* species has been widely investigated⁶. Presence of other secondary metabolites like thiophenes⁷, terpenes⁸, flavonoids⁹, carotenoids¹⁰ have also been reported from *Tagetes* species. Estimation of thiophenes from *T. patula* and other plants from *Asteraceae* family was reported¹¹. Here we report the distribution of biogenetically related thiophenes in three *Tagetes* spp. and their quantification using HPLC method.

Results and Discussion

The occurrence of thiophenes in leaves, roots and flowers of *Tagetes* species was found to vary drastically. The distribution of thiophenes in *T. patula* was found to be higher (Table 1) than in other *Tagetes* sp. *T. minuta* leaves carry more amount of thiophenes than roots, whereas in *T. patula* accumulation of thiophene is negligible. It can be

mentioned that roots and leaves are the two sites of accumulation of these compounds. The major source is *T. patula* roots followed by *T. Minuta* leaves. The accumulation of thiophene in the flowers was found to be in low concentration. These results agree with earlier reported data on distribution accumulation of thiophenes^{11,12}. The variation of thiophene concentration in leaves and roots suggests that accumulation of these compounds are not restricted to individual organs and roots and leaves have their own thiophene biosynthesis¹³.

Table 1. Analysis of thiophenes by HPLC

Species	Leaves (mg/ml)	Roots (mg/ml)	Flowers (mg/ml)
<i>T. minuta</i>	0.334	0.14	0.08
<i>T. patula</i>	Negligible	5.294	Negligible
<i>T. erecta</i>	0.038	0.016	0.020

Repeated column chromatography followed by MPLC of hexane fraction of the *T. minuta* roots resulted in isolation of six compounds. These compounds were identified with the help of UV, FT-IR, MS(EI), NMR (¹H, ¹³C and 2D NMR) comparison with literature data¹³⁻¹⁵, m.m.p., co-TLC with standard samples as 2,2' : 5'2''-terthienyl, 5-(3-buten-1-ynyl-2,2'-bithienyl), β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, octacosanol and 3-octacosanylstigmasterol. The ¹H and ¹³C values of thiophenes are given in Table 2.

Table 2. ¹H, ¹³C NMR spectral data of thiophenes

2,2' : 5'2''-Terthienyl :

No.	¹ H	¹³ C
1	—	—
2	—	137.6
3	7.17 (dd), J 3.4	123.7

[†]IHBT communication No. 2101.

Note

Table 2 (contd.)

4	7.02 (dd), J 5, 3.7	127.8
5	7.22 (dd), J 5.1	124.6
1'	—	—
2'	—	136.3
3'	7.07 (s)	124.3
4'	7.07 (s)	124.3
5'	—	—
5-(3-Buten-1-ynyl)-2,2'-bithienyl:		
1	—	—
2	—	138.9
3	7.03 (d), J 3.8	123.9
4	7.10 (d), J 3.8	132.8
5	—	121.6
1'	—	136.4
2'	—	124.1
3'	7.18 (dd)	127.8
4'	7.01 (dd), J 5.4	124.8
5'	7.23 (dd), J 5.1	—
1	—	83.6
2	—	93.2
3	6.02 (dd), J 17.5, 11	116.7
4	5.54 (dd), J 11, 2	126.7
4'	5.71 (dd), J 17.5, 2	—

Experimental

¹H NMR (400 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (100 MHz) spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, mass spectra on a 70 eV spectrometer, electronic spectra on a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer and FTIR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 1760X instrument. TLC was performed on silica gel G.

Different parts (leaves, flower and roots) of *T. minuta*, *T. patula* and *T. erecta* were collected from Institute's farm. The fresh parts (100 g each) were extracted with 90% methanol. The extracts were concentrated and partitioned with hexane. After concentration at 40° under reduced pressure, the fractions were dissolved in HPLC grade acetonitrile (5 ml). Thiophene (Fluka) was used as reference. All samples were filtered through 0.2 μ (Millipore) membrane and analyzed by Waters HPLC system. Column used was Waters Spherisorb (5μ, ODS-2, 4.6 × 250 nm analytical column) with solvent system 65 : 35 (water and acetonitrile), flowrate 1 ml/min, run time 45 min detector wavelength 231 nm.

For isolation of thiophenes and other compounds, powdered *T. minuta* roots (2 kg) were extracted with 90% methanol. The hexane fraction (5 g) on repeated column chromatography followed by separation on MPLC over silica gel (60–120 mesh, Qualigens) and hexane with increasing polarity of ethyl acetate yielded six compounds, identified with the help of spectroscopic techniques.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. P. S. Ahuja, Director, I.H.B.T., for constant encouragement during the course of the work.

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